

Coordination Complexes of Paludrine with Silver Nitrate and Mercuric Chloride

S. S. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL*

Chemical Laboratories, Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal (M.P.)

Manuscript received 7 September 1974; accepted 17 March 1975

Paludrine [1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-5-isopropyl biguanide], an antimalarial, form 1 : 2 coordination complexes with silver nitrate and mercuric chloride in alcoholic solutions as indicated by conductometric titrations. The complexes have been isolated and the analytical results confirm 1 : 2 ratio. Structures assigned are supported by I.R. spectral bands.

SILVER, mercury and their salts are having various therapeutic values. Therefore in continuation of our work on antimalarials¹⁻³, it was desired to study the complex formation of *p*-aludrine (I) with these metals.

Experimental

Materials and method

Purified paludrine base, m.p. 129° (lit. 130°) 0.005*M*, silver nitrate 0.01*M* AnalaR grade in purified 80% ethanol. Paludrine base and AnalaR mercuric chloride each 0.01*M* in 90% purified ethanol.

* Retd. Prof. of Applied Chemistry (M.P.E.S.), Holkar Science College, Indore.

10 ml paludrine 0.005*M* diluted to 200 ml and titrated with silver nitrate 0.01*M*, whereas in the titration against mercuric chloride 0.01*M*, 5 ml paludrine 0.01*M* diluted to 400 ml.

The conductometric titrations were carried out respectively at 18° and at 30° using Toshniwal conductivity bridge and dip type electrodes. After making the volume corrections the results are plotted in Fig. 1.

Isolation

(a) Paludrine base 1.0 g and silver nitrate 1.34 g in 1 : 2 molar proportions were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol. Base solution was added slowly to the metal solution with constant stirring. A white turbidity was seen after some time. On keeping the mixture in ice bath for about 20 hr, a brown coloured complex was obtained,

Fig. 1. AgNO₃ 0.01*M*, Paludrine 0.005*M*, temp. 18° HgCl₂ 0.01*M*, Paludrine 0.01*M*, temp. 30°.

which was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. Yield 1.5 g, m.p. 164°.

(b) Paludrine base 1.0 g and mercuric chloride 2.14 g in 1:2 molar proportions were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol. Base solution was added slowly to the mercuric chloride solution with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice bath for 4 hr, a white crystalline complex was obtained. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. Yield 2.3 g, m.p. 192°.

Analysis

Silver was estimated as chloride, mercury as sulphide and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method using modified digestion mixture {K₂SO₄ (5 g), CuSO₄ (0.1 g), mercuric oxide (0.3 g), selenium powder (0.1 g) and glucose (1 g)} c.f. also⁴. Chloride and base were estimated by usual methods. The analytical results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Composition of the complex	%	Ag/Hg	Ionisable Cl	N	Base-HCl
C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₅ Cl : 2Ag	Found	46.70	-	14.03	-
	Requires	46.16	-	14.98	-
C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₅ Cl : 2HgCl	Found	55.04	9.33	9.24	38.37
	Requires	55.46	9.82	9.68	40.09

Discussion

The conductometric titration results plotted in Fig. 1 clearly indicate that paludrine forms 1:2 and 2:1 complexes with silver and 1:2 complex with mercury. In case of Ag and Hg, the complexation with paludrine takes place in a somewhat different manner as compared to Cu, Fe and Co salts. Paludrine-silver complex does not give the test for nitrate and is insoluble in water. The analysis agrees with the composition C₁₁H₁₄N₅Cl(Ag)₂. The formation takes place according to the reaction

showing that 2H atoms of the paludrine molecule are eliminated in the reaction. It may be assigned the structures (II) or (III).

In structure (II) the hydrogens at N¹ and N⁵ are replaced by silver and in structure (III), this replacement is shown to have taken place at N² and N⁴ nitrogens. In structure (II) the hydrogen attached to aryl amino and alkyl amino nitrogens at N¹ and N⁵ are shown to protonate; whereas in structure (III) hydrogen attached to -C = NH group protonates. Structure (III) is supported by the anilino absorption band observed at 1285 cm⁻¹ in the infra red spectra of the complex.

Paludrine mercuric chloride complex 1:2 is sparingly soluble in water and the analytical results agree with the composition C₁₁H₁₄N₅Cl : 2HgCl. Therefore, in analogy with paludrine-2Ag complex (III), the paludrine-2HgCl complex may be assigned the structure (IV).

Here again the infra-red spectra of the complex shows an absorption band at 1290 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of anilino group. Further the structures (III) and (IV) of Ag and Hg complexes get support by absorption bands at 1170±10 and 1640±5 cm⁻¹, characteristic of -NH-CH(CH₃)₂.

It may be mentioned that Ray and Siddanta⁵ prepared a biguanide mercuric complex to which they gave the structure (V).

In view of their own work on biguanide complexes of metals^{6,7} and the structures assigned to various paludrine metal complexes by us, the structure (V) does not appear to be tenable. Therefore, it may be represented by the structure (VI), consistent with other complexes of biguanides.

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